

EXPLOITING KEY INFORMATION FROM OPEN SCIENTIFIC SEARCH RESULTS TO ENHANCE USER EXPERIENCE

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Abstract

Search engines have become essential tools for users searching for relevant information. This paper proposes an approach to extract key information from open scientific search results and uses aspect-based summarization to improve user experience and search efficiency. The resulting system allows for fine-tuning of search results by selecting them, and then extracts aspect-based summaries from each to relate and compare them to each other, e.g. the research questions, used methods, and evaluation metrics.

INTRODUCTION

Given the wealth of information available on the Web, open search engines have become important tools for users looking for relevant information. Although in the past, it was customary to provide simple lists of links as search results, this has now become an increasingly outdated approach. Instead, search engines have evolved to provide additional information, such as images, videos, and other multimedia content, on search results pages [18], and more recently, conversational information retrieval systems have become increasingly popular. Tools such as ChatGPT (Generative Pre-trained Transformer) and the usage of language models have revolutionized user search behavior, regardless of the potential remaining issues regarding factual accuracy to the result's source material [9]. However, while conversational AI is a promising method for many problems, some applications may benefit from using other, more explainable approaches. When searching for scientific papers, for example, it is essential that the summary correctly reflects the information contained in the source document. In addition, the consistent structure of scientific papers makes it possible to make some assumptions regarding its most relevant contents. This article proposes a concept for the aspect-based summarization of one or a small number of selected scientific search results, focusing on aspects such as "Motivation", "Hypothesis", and "Research questions", as well as filtering options for quality metrics related to these aspects.

Thus, this research aims to improve the user search experience and the effectiveness of information acquisition by providing key information about user-selected search results. It specifically seeks to answer the following two questions:

The next section will provide an overview of the related work, particularly in regard to search, question answering, key information extraction, and aspect-based summarization.

Following this, we will give a detailed explanation of the concept, after which we will further describe the development. Subsequently, the results will be shown and discussed. Finally, the work ends with the conclusion.

RELATED WORK

As the amount of content on the Web grows, search engines must adapt to changing requirements. Although traditionally search results were presented as lists of links with short information excerpts, this is no longer the only approach, particularly in the scientific field, where websites such as Elicit aim to give a more in-depth overview of search results by extracting key information such as "Abstract summary", "Intervention", and "Outcome measured" [13].

In recent years, the presentation of search results has rapidly shifted to using question-answering as its methodology of choice. Question answering aims to provide direct and concise answers to queries, such as in answer boxes at the top of search results or through the use of chatbots. However, the effectiveness of question answering depends heavily on how search results are presented, as well as on the correct understanding of the question itself. Current solutions place a great deal of emphasis on interactive question answering, in part due to recent progress in the use of machine learning for this task [3].

Although machine learning has been leveraged to this effect with promising results, when the user's goal is to get an overview of a select number of search results, the issue remains that the main method of presenting this information is via small previews only, thus making it necessary to open each web page to get a clear idea whether it is relevant. As this is not only the case for web search, previous research in other fields has also taken note of this issue. Ma et al. describe a system for automatic extraction of key elements from geological hazard documents and visualize the results as knowledge graphs [11]. They utilized the TF-IDF algorithm for keyword extraction and visualized them with methods such as word clouds. Furthermore, Ma et al. performed cluster analysis based on co-occurrence to discover relations.

Although aspect-based summarization has been an active field of research for years, much of it has been in the domain of reviews and combined with sentiment analysis [6, 15]. Research on aspect-based summarization in scientific settings is limited, and even more so for scientific search. However, the approach may serve to improve both the user search experience and the efficiency of information acquisition when used to improve search engines, as aspect-based summariza-

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tion has already been found to be particularly useful for tasks such as opinion mining, judgment labeling, and personalized learning environments [10, 19].

Aspect-based summarization involves generating a summary that focuses on a specific aspect or topic within a given document. Ravi and Ravi provided a comprehensive survey on opinion mining and sentiment analysis, which are closely related to aspect-based summarization [14]. The survey covers tasks, approaches, and applications in sentiment analysis, offering valuable insight into the broader context of opinion-based summarization. Frermann and Klementiev addressed the task of aspect-based summarization by developing models that generate summaries centered on specific aspects within a document [5]. Their work contributes to the methodology of aspect-based summarization and provides valuable techniques for aspect-focused summarization. Tan et al. proposed a knowledge-informed, weakly supervised approach for summarizing text on various aspects [17]. Their work contributes to the development of techniques for generating aspect-based abstractive summaries.

Although user attitudes towards personalized aspect-based summarization have long been evaluated and have generally been found to favor personalization with respect to, among other things, summary length [2], aspect-based summarization for search results has received little attention. Frermann and Klementiev aimed to summarize news articles by the aspects (or topics) they covered, leveraging the mostly consistent structure of news articles and encoder-decoder models [5]. Hayashi et al. (2021) introduced the WikiAsp dataset, which specifically addresses multi-domain aspect-based summarization [7]. This dataset has been instrumental in advancing research on aspect-based summarization by providing a standardized benchmark for evaluating summarization models across different domains. In the scientific domain, Ment et al. presented FacetSum [12]. However, the dataset, which covered multiple domains, included only a specific set of facets (Purpose, Method, Findings, and Value). This limitation was also noted by Soleimani et al., who similarly aimed to extend their method for other aspects of the FacetSum and PubMed datasets [16]. They did so by leveraging semantic representations from the pre-training process to establish similarity between aspects and content.

The lack of a large dedicated data set was another limitation for aspect-based summarization. Only recently have additional datasets been published specifically for aspect-based summarization tasks. In an attempt to address the domain-specific nature of both models and datasets, [7] and [20] published large-scale open-domain datasets for aspect-based summarization tasks.

CONCEPT

Backed by the literature review in the previous section, this paper aims to take advantage of recent advances in automatic summarization to provide users with more precise and relevant information regarding their search results. The proposed method will integrate aspect-based summarization

Figure 1: User/search engine interactions for the proposed system

techniques to enhance the retrieval and presentation of information by summarizing individual or small numbers of scientific papers. The objective is to improve the user experience and speed up information acquisition by preventing users from having to leave the search results page to get the required information.

Instead of a simple list of results, the user has the option of selecting specific aspects of the content that they are particularly interested in and having them briefly summarized. By doing this, the idea is to create a system that allows for the selection of search results and then extracts the most salient information from each to relate and compare it to each other, e.g. the research questions, used methods, and evaluation metrics of scientific papers. Ideally, this would take place after or at the same time as the search for specific search terms, as can be seen in Figure 1.

As scientific papers generally have a similar structure, it is possible to define a set of key information of particular interest. Table ?? gives a brief overview of the selected points that were considered of particular interest to a potential user and should be summarized from the selected document(s), as well as function as filtering criteria. The result of the

search process is then a list of papers that include the given keyword, as well as match the filtering criteria for the defined facets.

By extracting these aspects, it is possible to filter according to whether they are present in a document, how extensively they are covered, and score the suitability of sources according to the number and quality of the aspects they contain.

This aim was achieved by building on previous work from [12] and [8]. The FacetSum model specifically summarized for a selection of different facets (see Table 2, which was extended for this research and is intended to contain all the facets of Table ?? in the future.

Due to the dataset used by [12] containing only the facets Purpose, Method, Findings, and Value, it was necessary to create an own dataset and extend it with the additional required facets. Furthermore, the facets as given in our table divide Purpose into different facets, namely Motivation and Research questions.

DEVELOPMENT

The prototype described in this article is an extension of some of the work done in previous research [4, 12]. The implementation consisted of an extension of existing extractable facets. This involved, in the first step, an extension of data, which was done manually for a small dataset of 40 articles.

The choice of method was made due to the requirements of the selected use case. Extraction of specific facets requires an understanding of context that exceeds the possibilities of many language models. Although transformer-based methods show more promise for this process, many require large amounts of resources to run. With this in mind, the goal was also to select a comparatively small model due to further pre-training that may be required to adapt the model to be able to extract further facets. Furthermore, the selection of the model must consider the length of the intended input. Due to the average length of scientific papers outstripping that of many other possible types of input such as news articles and blog posts, the model has to be able to handle long input texts. This is not the case with many language models, which set the maximum number of tokens quite low; in the case of BERT, this is 512, where each token can be considered to function as a word and is not sufficient for scientific papers.

The pipeline itself, which is depicted in Figure 2 was created using a number of different libraries that were essential for functionality. The scientific articles used for the testing process were published in the Journal of Universal Computer Science and downloaded in pdf form. Then they were fed to GROBID, which extracts and parses text from PDFs into easily traversable XML structures. We then collected the relevant data for each article which are as follows: title of the article, author(s), abstract text, conclusion text and full text of the article. For the research phase, this was further

Figure 2: Flowchart of the project architecture

extended manually by adding reference summaries for each facet to enable evaluation of the results.

Once the dataset is done, each paper's data is fed to the facet summarization method(s). One or more of these can be selected before running the pipeline to get the results for each approach. For this paper, we based our work on FacetSum and SLED, with the possibility of extending the selection further in the future to gain additional insights into comparisons of result qualities. The resulting output, the facet summaries, are then rated according to their length. Depending on whether a summary is below 15 words, between 16 and 25, or above 25 words, it receives the attribute "short", "medium", or "long", respectively. Further fine-tuning may be needed for future research, depending on the paper domain(s), type of paper, and generally average aspect summary lengths.

Facet	Prompt	Keywords
MOT	Motivation	Motivation, goal, aim
HYP	Hypothesis	Hypothesis, expectation
RQ	Research questions	RQ, research question
CON	Contribution	Contribution, add
RW	Related work	Related work, basis, previous research
RM	Research methods	Methods, methodology, process
TL	Tools, libraries used in research	Library, package, application
TD	Test data used for training and testing	Data set, training data, test data
EM	Metrics used for result evaluation	Evaluation, quality, reliability, score
MF	Main findings of the research	Findings, outcome, result
LIM	Limitations, issues found during the research	Limitations, issues, problems, exception
FW	Future directions and work	future, next, improvements

Table 1: Facet abbreviations with their prompt and associated keywords. Inspired by Table 1 by Ahuja et al. [1]

Facet	FacetSum	This paper
Motivation	Yes(?)	Yes
Hypothesis		Yes
Research questions	Yes(?)	Yes
Contributions	Yes	Yes
Related work		
Research methods	Yes	Yes
Tools/Libraries		Yes
Test data		
Evaluation metrics		
Main findings/outcomes	Yes	Yes
Limitations		
Further directions		
Data source		

Table 2: Comparison of covered facets

Following this, a score is given to the paper based on the number of facets present. This is done by counting the number of existing facet summaries of all possible facets. Furthermore, this is the point where, for the research process, we calculated the rouge scores for the summaries and saved them to files to be able to evaluate the result quality.

The extracted facets from the various papers are put into comparison with each other by creating a CSV table containing basic paper information (title, authors) as well as the facet summaries.

RESULTS

First outcomes using this approach showed promising results. Summarization was performed for a selection of the intended aspects to evaluate the feasibility of extending the original language model to cover other aspects.

CONCLUSION

This paper proposes an approach to extracting key information from scientific search results and presenting information from multiple sources by displaying them in relation to each other. The resulting system allows for fine-tuning of search results by selecting them and then extracting key

Facet	Result
Motivation	
Hypothesis	
Research questions	
Contributions	
Research methods	
Main findings	

Table 3: Caption

points from each. When presenting the extracted information in relation to each other, it becomes easier to see how certain results fit into the larger body of research work and facilitates a more effective search experience.

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